

CLASSIFICATIONS OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT BASED ON "PEDAGOGY" IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract.

This article presents professional competence, ways to develop teacher's professional competence in teaching "Pedagogy" in primary education.

Key words:

competence, professional development, education, self-development.

Абстрактный.

В данной статье представлены профессиональная компетентность, пути развития профессиональной компетентности учителя при преподавании дисциплины «Педагогика» в системе начального образования.

Ключевые слова:

компетентность, профессиональное развитие, образование, саморазвитие.

INTRODUCTION .

When thinking about the organization and development of the educational process, its essence is made up of three interconnected factors: teaching, upbringing and development.

The result of qualitative and structural changes implemented in the higher education system in the context of its radical renewal is aimed at the professional and personal improvement of the teacher. We combine these two most important qualities of a specialist in the concept of "pedagogical competence" and believe that it includes personal skills and creative abilities, high intelligence, spiritual and cultural abilities. Ethical values, in short, are the formation of higher education in the humanistic educational system and a certain dream of a continuously developing specialist who can realize his human and professional potential with the greatest efficiency in specific activities. is a made image. This can be achieved through self-education and self-improvement.

Modern society requires the education system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the 2017-2021 action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a pool of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" was set.[1]

Methodological analysis. The concept of "professional competence" entered the field of education as a result of several practical studies and researches. Including N.A. Muslimov, M.Kh.Usmonboyeva, D.M.Sayfurov, A.B.Torayev conducted scientific research and defined it as follows: Professional competence is the acquisition of the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application. is to be applied at the level.[2]

The types of competence according to R. Markova's classification are as follows:

- a. Special pedagogical competence
- b. Social pedagogical competence
- c. Personal pedagogical competence
- d. Individual competence

The main factor that forms the teacher's competence is special professional education. Development of professional competences of future elementary school teachers, preparation for teaching based on an integrative approach, scientific-research works, various directions and principles of interdisciplinary communication, their use in mastering certain subjects in the educational process, scientific-practical aspects of the requirements for the content of education based on interdisciplinary communication N.M.Abdullayeva, M.Ashirova, T.Dayanayeva, R.A.Mavlonova, A.Musurmonov, P.Musayev, R.G'.Safarova, E.O.Turdikulov, A. Researched in the works of Ch. Choriyev, Sh. E. Qurbanov, Sh. Yusupova.

Qualities of teacher's professional competence[3]:

- Formation of students' motivation;
- Ability to plan, evaluate, and establish feedback on the educational process;
- Knowledge of information and communication technologies;
- Work on oneself;
- To have knowledge of pedagogy and psychology;
- Perfect knowledge of one's subject;
- Bringing innovation to the educational environment;

Professional competence can include competence in professional activities, competence in professional communication, and the competence of a specialist to demonstrate his profession. The following recommendations should be followed in order to develop the professional competencies of primary school teachers based on the science of education:

1. Planning topics in educational programs with the wide use of national education methods: planning while integrating our rich spiritual heritage, the works of great thinkers and scientists, the life and creativity of the children of the patriot and righteous country into the topics;

2. Creating manuals and videos promoting national values, customs, and traditions: creating videos and manuals about the Islamic religion, national ideology, national holidays, and traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation for centuries, on the basis of this knowledge, it is possible to teach and develop professional competences;

3. Developing their own national textbooks, online platforms, and electronic training manuals for teacher training using the teaching methods of foreign advanced countries: the students' lessons through electronic and online platforms provide students with information makes it easier to find;

4. Organization of interactive lessons: interactive lessons organized by the teacher help to put students' knowledge into practice.

5. Development of training programs: Students are facilitated to improve their professional competence by developing training programs. Also, in this form, students can take a "practice" test.

A teacher can achieve a good result if he remembers that the program is not for students, but for students; presents the material in a clear, reasonable and systematic way, revealing the necessary and clear connections and dependencies; adapts the learning pace to the needs of the majority of students who are subject to individual work behind schedule; uses reasonable forms of oral, written, computer control, interests students in achieving maximum learning results, while developing their motivation to learn.

It can be said with confidence that in the modern world there is a tendency to combine education and information technologies, and on this basis, in particular, based on Internet technologies, fundamentally new integrated educational technologies are being formed. With the use of such technologies, the possibility of unlimited and very cheap reproduction of educational information, its quick and targeted delivery has appeared. At the same time, education will be interactive, the

importance of students' independent work will increase, the intensity of the learning process will seriously increase, etc.

However, it is also worth noting that some pedagogical problems encountered in the educational process prevent the professional development of the teacher and reduce the quality of the educational process by preventing him from working on himself. Examples of such situations include the low culture of teacher communication, the unfriendly social environment in the pedagogical team, the failure to establish the mentor-student tradition, the general potential of specialists in the pedagogical team, and the lack of control over young personnel, etc. we can show. Every future teacher who graduates from universities and enters an educational institution must have the following professional qualities:

- professional activity
- creative approach;
- independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences;
- show activity in creating new ideas;
- share ideas with colleagues about pedagogical achievements.

The self-development and professional growth of each pedagogue is directly related to his creative ability. Usually, the creative ability of pedagogues is ensured by striving to solve pedagogical problems, carrying out scientific research or scientific projects, and achieving mutual creative cooperation.

Effective pedagogical communication is the most important component of a teacher's professional activity. Communication in pedagogical activity is a means of solving educational problems, a means of socio-psychological support of the educational process, a method of organizing relations between teachers and students, and determines the success of education and upbringing. However, not all young teachers who have graduated do not meet the current requirements. According to O.V.Litovchenko's research, more than 54% of young teachers are unable to motivate students to learn, and 51% report a lack of knowledge and skills in teaching methodology, which is a direct result of insufficiently developed skills. Therefore, the current situation requires a special approach to the formation of this preparation in the student of the higher educational institution of pedagogy.

The professional competence development system is presented in the form of a program of joint activities between the teacher and students. This program is an algorithm of joint activity, in which the student is both the subject and the object of the educational process. When developing a student's professional development program, it is necessary to take into account the factors that block the motivational-valuable attitude to teaching work and slow down professional growth:

1) Difficulties in communication: inability to get out of a difficult educational situation; problems in organizing effective activities, lack of communication techniques.

2) Difficulties in self-management, lack of awareness of one's own behavior, feelings, appearance, oneself, capabilities and characteristics, one's condition, feelings and not being able to regulate their behavior, not being able to analyze their own activities.

3) Difficulties in developing an individual style of professional activity.

The teacher's professional activity depends on how he understands the moral responsibility for the result of his work. The existence of conditions for the professional development of future teachers in the higher education system is an important factor in improving the quality of professional training.

Professional development of students, if the following conditions are met in the educational process, will reach a level sufficient for the implementation of professional pedagogical activity:

- socio-pedagogical experience becomes a necessary condition for the development of personal experience;
- orientation to professional development –systematic reflection helps to develop it sufficiently for the implementation of professional-pedagogical activities;
- in the pedagogical practice aimed at professional development, personal experience is collected, which is useful for understanding the teaching abilities of students.

Conclusion. With the times and rapid changes in society, teachers are now taking on the challenge of "teaching using new pedagogy". Teachers are moving away from the traditional form of teaching and rethinking their learning partnerships with children and are making good use of digital technologies to extend the learning environment locally, globally and virtually. On the other hand, it cannot be said that the scientific research of teachers in the new era has sufficiently studied the professional abilities and competences of teachers. However, when discussing the professional development of a teacher in Uzbekistan and around the world, the knowledge, thinking, values, beliefs, values, feelings, motivation, etc. defined as the qualifications of teachers are expressed by the broad criteria of the teaching profession. are part of the range of competencies. In addition, although the core of a teacher's activity is teaching, it covers various special activities, interactions with children, colleagues, parents and society.

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